

Horizon 2020
European Union Funding
for Research & Innovation

Viscoelastic properties of the flagellum

Deliverable 1.3

H2020-MSCA-ITN-2020 PHYMOT

Physics of Microbial Motility

Grant Agreement Nr.: 955910

Lead beneficiary UIB

Coordinator Gerhard Gompper

Workpackage 1

V1.0 10/01/2022

V2.0 22/02/2022

V3.0 05/05/2022

Due date

First submission (draft)

Submission revision 2.0

Dissemination level

<https://etn-phymot.eu>

Luc Zorilla & Marco Polin

G. Vliegthart added title page

G. Vliegthart added acknowledgement

31/01/2022

January 2022

23/02/2022

Public

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955910.

Review - On the viscoelastic properties of the axoneme of eukaryotic flagella

Luc Zorrilla

Supervisor: Marco Polin

January 2022

1 Introduction

Living organisms can be separated into different domains. One of these fundamental domains is the Eukaryota. Eukaryotes are uni- or multi-cellular organisms whose genetic code is comprised within the nucleus of each cell, as opposed to prokaryotes where there is no nucleus. The nucleus is an organelle, one of the functional machines of the cell. Another one of importance in eukaryotes is the flagellum, a hair-like protrusion comprising the membrane (a continuation of the cell's), the axoneme located beneath it forming the "bone" structure, and the basal body in the inner side of the cell surrounding the part of the axoneme inside the cell.

Flagella or cilia are widely common in the eukaryotic domain and in humans in particular as it provides essential functions to the cell. These functions can either be sensing of mechanical and chemical stimuli or motility. In fact, one can roughly distinguish two types of flagella: primary flagella which are non-motile and ubiquitous in the human organism, that serve primarily as sensors of external stimuli; and motile flagella which include molecular motors to induce motion through a medium. One of the key differences between these two flagella is the structure of their axoneme. In both cases axonemes are made of microtubule doublets, but what changes is the number and configuration of these doublets as well as what connects them. In primary flagella, there are 9 microtubule doublets arranged in a circular fashion, with no or almost no connection between them. However motile cilia also have a central pair of microtubule doublets, as well as several other components: radial spokes connected between the central pair and each outer doublet, nexin links connected between adjacent outer doublets, and dynein arms constantly connecting and disconnecting between adjacent outer doublets through ATP hydrolysis. These dynein arms are local molecular motors that make outer microtubules slide between one another, which in turn produces local bending ([17] & Figure 1) and ultimately the beating pattern of the flagellum.

Figure 1: The sliding microtubule model. Dynein arms produce interdoublet sliding. Assuming no sliding at base and circular shape, bending angle and sliding distance are linearly related. Taken from [3]

Of course, the distinction and description given here between primary and motile flagella is not complete. There are many more differences between and within the two types – for example in the basal body – and there are more components not described here, either in the axoneme, the basal body or the membrane. Furthermore, there exist slight differences from one species to another as we will see when looking case by case in this review. The key point is that flagella are highly conserved structures because they are an essential organelle of eukaryotic cells. This also motivates their understanding as it is fundamental in cell biology.

Of particular interest for a physicist is to understand the mechanical properties of flagella. In particular, what are the mechanical properties of the axoneme? One could ask what are its material properties: how stiff is it, how viscous? Understanding these characteristics could help – and has helped – to understand the structure of flagella, how they beat, how are beating patterns created, if mechanical sensing is at all possible and how is a signal transmitted to the cell. The aim of this review is to give a summary of our current answers to the following question: *What are the viscoelastic properties of the axoneme of eukaryotic flagella?* In particular, I am interested in the role of axoneme mechanical properties in bending. If need be, the role of the axoneme will be compared to the role of the basal body – or the membrane – in bending. I will use an historical approach to show how the knowledge is built and put into question along time, to finish with a summary of current knowledge, doubts and perspectives that are in the scientific community about this question. The first chapter deals with motile flagella while the second chapter deals with primary cilia, followed by a conclusion.

2 Mechanical properties of motile flagella

Introduction Motile flagella beat in their medium at low Reynolds number, hence they need a non-symmetrical beating pattern to produce an overall movement [20]: the power stroke pushing them in the "forward direction" by force and the recovery stroke pushing them backwards, but less far since the move-

ment is more flexible and there is less drag (Figure 3). Motile flagella axoneme are called "9+2" axonemes as they are made of 9 outer microtubule doublets and one central pair of microtubule doublets. We also know that dynein ATPases – outer doublet arms – are directly responsible for microtubule doublet sliding via outer doublets cross bridging through ATP dephosphorylation. If flagella have access to ATP, they will beat because their dynein arms will use the energy of these ATP molecules to produce microtubule sliding by attaching and detaching between outer doublets, which has been found to be directly related to bending [17] and thus beating. Our knowledge of the structure of the axoneme of motile cilia is evolving a lot throughout the decades. What we know is that there are radial spokes between outer doublets and the central pair, outer dynein arms and inner dynein arms both actively binding to the adjacent outer doublet, nexin-dynein regulatory complex permanently connected between outer doublets, as can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Structure of the axoneme. Left image shows an idealized cross-section representation of the axonemal structure, right image shows a molecular model of an outer doublet surrounding structure.

I begin this review with motile flagella, as the study of their mechanical properties starts quite early, as soon as 1971. Baba [1] assessed the bending response of a *Mytilus Edulis* (blue mussel) large abfrontal cilium to a micro-needle push during the power stroke, either against the power stroke direction or in the same direction (Figure 4). They measured the bending moment to the cilium as due to the micro-needle elasticity K and viscous drag R of the medium on the micro-needle, and measured the needle displacement D and the change in flagellum curvature $\gamma - \gamma_0$ due to the microneedle before and after external forcing, at the point of force application. The force applied to the

Figure 3: Stroboscopic image of a beat cycle of Chlamydomonas. The power stroke (roughly) ranges from 1 to 11 while the recovery stroke ranges from 13 to 27, resulting in a small displacement to the left. Adapted from [4]

flagellum is $F = KD + R\frac{dD}{dt}$, plus the resistance of the medium of the ciliary shaft using resistive force theory, thus giving the total bending moment exerted on the cilium.

Fig. 1. Diagram showing the principle of determination of the flexural rigidity of the cilium. (a) The sequence of a part of a normal stroke (interval: 11 msec) and the path (dashed line) of the tip (circles) of a needle. (b) and (c) show that the change of the curvature of the ciliary shaft occurs in response to the force (arrows) applied to the cilium by the needle.

Figure 4: Figure 1 of [1]

They find that in both directions of the needle movement – either against or with the stroke – changes in curvature happen at the same time as changes in the bending moment: there is no observable delay between the two. Also the curvature retrieves its initial state when the cilium is released from the microneedle. These two observations indicate a **purely elastic behaviour**. The ratio of the bending moment to the change in curvature is defined as the *flexural rigidity*, and is supposed to be constant for an homogeneous, isotropic material and equal to

$$EI = \frac{M}{\gamma - \gamma_0}$$

This is the case here: flexural rigidity is found to be constant along the length of the cilium and – apparently – regardless of the stroke phase. One can see though that flexural rigidity reduces with flagellum diameter. This is consistent

with the fact that *Mytilus Edulis* abfrontal flagella are composed of multiple eukaryotic motile flagella. These component flagella are enclosed independently in the large abfrontal flagellum as the number of components is found to be proportional to the cross-sectional area. Hence the flexural rigidity of one component flagellum is the flexural rigidity of the large flagellum divided by the number of components. It is found to be of $EI = 3 * 10^{-19} N.m^2$. No standard deviation is given, but given standard deviations for compound flagella and adding variations from cross-section measurements, one can take this value as a simple order of magnitude. In any case, at that time the structural origin of the found elasticity was unclear. Given microtubule flexural rigidity [11] $EI_{MT} = 8 * 10^{-24} N.m^2$ – a still debated value – and assuming independence between them in flagella, one gets $EI_{no\ link} = 8.8 * 10^{-23} N.m^2$, which is much lower than the value found in this article, so **microtubules cannot be the mere cause of flexural rigidity**. A more thorough computation is given taking into account radial links and arms between doublets and is consistent with flexural rigidity (or bending stiffness) of microtubules and of flagella. Hence resistance to bending could be due to microtubules connected between each other in a tight fashion. However, one does not yet know the role of the membrane in bending.

Gibbons & al [8] have discovered **two states of rigidity in demembrated sea urchin sperm flagella depending on ATP concentration**. Reducing abruptly the ATP concentration (by drastic dilution) shows rigor waves of flagella stopped in different phases of their beating pattern: this is the **rigor state**. Even when nexin links and radial spokes were digested by trypsin, the rigor state was conserved, suggesting that **dynein cross-bridging alone is responsible for this state**. Adding a small quantity of ATP – but not enough to produce continuous beating – to flagella in the rigor state will relax these rigor waves and straighten them: this is the **relaxed state**. Okuno [16] extend this result by looking at rigidity states of demembrated sea urchin sperm flagella in the presence of ATP and vanadate. When vanadate and ATP are both present in the solution, rigor waves relax and flagella reach a relaxed state. First, demembrated flagella were reactivated in a solution containing ATP, and abruptly diluted in a solution with no ATP to produce rigor states as in Gibbons & al [8]. Then stiffness measurements were made in the spirit of Baba & al [1] with different concentrations of ATP and vanadate. It was found as in Gibbons & al that increasing slowly ATP – without vanadate – yields first a relaxed state until beating starts again. Adding vanadate in the presence of ATP prevented beating, and even accelerated relaxation. In fact, they found that ATP dephosphorylation is prevented by vanadate. No such relaxation was found in the presence of ADP, though: the rigor state remained. As thought, the rigor state and the relaxed state could be differentiated by their flexural rigidity, with no influence of vanadate concentration: $EI_{rigor} = 1.5 * 10^{-20} N.m^2$ while $EI_{relaxed} = 0.9 * 10^{-21} N.m^2$, 15 times lower. The value for the rigor state is somewhat lower than in Baba & al [1]. This might be due to high uncertainties in these measurements, or to the role of the membrane. Another possibility is the flagellar length, which is on average twice lower for these sea urchin sperm flagella than for abfrontal flagella of *Mytilus Edulis*: would flexural rigidity be length dependent? It was found later [24] that ATP, or ATP and vanadate

produces detachment of cross-links between outer doublet. This suggests that the **reduction in rigidity between the rigor state and the relaxed state can be due to dynein arms detachment**. However, there must still be some connection between microtubule doublets to account for the observed flexural rigidity, as we discarded the role of the membrane in this experiment.

A question arises naturally: what is the role of each structural element to flexural rigidity? Ishijima & al [9] answer it by carefully examining the elastic bending response to hydrodynamic flow of echinoderm sperm flagella that are either alive, demembranated, reactivated or even trypsin-digested including isolated microtubule doublets measurements. They also looked at differences between bending in the beating plane and perpendicular to it. For beating flagella, flexural rigidity in the beating plane is determined as the ratio between the moment of the fluid flow on the flagellum, over the change in curvature between underflow equilibrium and resting equilibrium. For bending in the transverse plane, assuming the flagellum is isotropic and incompressible one can relate torsion to pure bending. This allows to compute flexural rigidity from the measured deflection at the tip – caused by both pure bending and torsion. For bending of motionless flagella or isolated microtubules, if one assumes again an isotropic elastic rod flexural rigidity is deduced from tip deflection. For all experiments the moment of fluid flow on the system is computed from resistive force theory. Results are recorded in Figure 5.

Table I. FLEXURAL RIGIDITY OF SAND DOLLAR SPERM FLAGELLA (10^{-21} Nm²).

	Motionless flagella		Beating flagella				
	Medium	n	Medium	a*	n	b†	n
Live flagella	CO ₂ -saturated SW	11 ± 6 (13)	Normal SW	0.42 ± 0.31 (24)		5.8 ± 2.6 (10)	
	2 mM EHNA, ASW	0.19 ± 0.04 (16)					
Demembranated flagella	0 mM ATP	14 ± 4 (17)	1 mM ATP	1.0 ± 0.6 (16)		12 ± 3 (8)	
	2 μM ATP	15 ± 8 (13)					
	1 mM ATP, 10 μM vanadate	0.31 ± 0.15 (15)					
	1 mM ATP, 2 mM EHNA	0.28 ± 0.09 (12)					
Trypsin-digested demembranated flagella	0 mM ATP	16 ± 5 (10)					
Doublet microtubules	0 mM ATP	0.061–0.23 (11)					
	0.1 mM ATP	0.014–0.38 (13)					

Mean ± SD. Results from three to six experiments were averaged. n, number of spermatozoa measured.

* Bending in the beating plane.

† Bending in the direction perpendicular to the beating plane.

Figure 5: Table 1 of [9]

Stiffness parallel to the beating plane is of the same order of magnitude for alive flagella beating in Natural Sea Water as for ATP-reativated demembranated flagella: $EI_{parallel} = 0.4 - 1 * 10^{-21} N.m^2$. As well, stiffness of (ATP+vanadate)-relaxed demembranated flagella is of $EI_{relax} = 0.4 ± 0.3 * 10^{-21} N.m^2$, the same order of magnitude as for alive flagella immobilized by EHNA in Artificial Sea Water. These results are consistent with Okuno's previous experiments [16] and imply that **the membrane is not accounting for stiffness** either, during beating or not. Measured stiffness in trypsin-digested demembranated flagella is of $EI = 1.6 ± 0.5 * 10^{-20} N.m^2$. This is the same order of magnitude as for ATP-free demembranated flagella. Thus **radial spokes and nexin links are not accounting for stiffness in motionless flagella**. For beating live flagella or for reactivated demembranated flagella, stiffness perpendicular to the beating plane is of the order of $EI_{orthogonal} = 10^{-20} N.m^2$,

which is one order of magnitude higher than stiffness within the beating plane. Under the assumption that it is dynein cross-links between microtubule doublets that are responsible for the stiffness in flagella, this result implies that **dynein arms are engaged in much greater number between microtubules perpendicular to the beating plane, rather than between microtubules parallel to the beating plane**. This is supported by the fact that stiffness parallel to the beating plane for beating flagella is of similar value as stiffness of a relaxed, demembranated flagella (ATP+vanadate), which itself accounts for 2% of the stiffness for ATP-free demembranated flagella. Since the relaxed state has most of its dynein arms disengaged, those within the beating plane are probably mostly disengaged as well. However this paper and the previous ones all assumed a model of elastic beam for the resistance to bending, which is not complete.

Indeed, on top of the pure bending mechanism coming from elastic beam theory, motile flagella also exhibit sliding resistance because doublets slide relatively to each other thanks to dynein activity. Some experiments [26] show that microtubule doublets slide freely in isolated trypsin-digested axonemes in presence of ATP: mechanical links between doublets thus prevent sliding. Minoura & al [14] measured for the first time elastic resistance to sliding and attribute it to elasticity between outer doublets during sliding. Isolated, demembranated flagella of *Chlamydomonas* are first stuck to a coverslip, then one attaches a microneedle tip perpendicularly to the axoneme axis. Shear in the axonemal direction is performed with the glass needle of known stiffness. Displacement of the microneedle base and of tip displacement are recorded and give the axonemal stiffness (Figure 6). They found an **elastic response of the axoneme to longitudinal shear deformation**. Measured elastic stiffness per micrometer of axoneme is $k_{ATP} = 2.0 \pm 0.8 pN/nm$ when ATP or ATP and vanadate are present and $k_{\overline{ATP}} = 10 pN/nm$ without ATP. Cross-bridging dynein arms increase stiffness to five times the value in which they are not strongly bound between outer doublets. Measurement is also made for mutants pf18 (no central pair), pf14 (no radial spokes) and oda (no outer dynein arms). All mutants exhibit the same stiffness as the wild type. These results imply that **shear resistance is due to interdoublet links** since it increases with tight dynein binding (no ATP) and mutant that lack components not involved in interdoublet linking show no measurable change in stiffness. Whether half of the outer doublets slide with respect to the other half (parallel configuration) or all doublets move relative to each other (serie configuration), the contribution to sliding resistance could change. The parallel configuration is backed up by experiments on axoneme disintegration that shows that two groups tend to separate [27].

Nexin – a part of the nexin-dynein regulatory complex – has been found to bridge between outer doublets every $96nm$ and could be the cause of sliding resistance. Assuming nexin links stretch evenly along the structure and that sliding resistance is only between two rows of doublets (parallel configuration), there are about 20 nexin links involved per micrometer of axoneme. Shear resistance of one nexin link would thus be of $k_{nexin} = 0.1 pN/nm$. Interestingly, stepwise displacements of the microprobe tip are also observed when ATP is present – in both directions. One could argue that nexins cooperatively detach

Fig. 1. Schematic drawing of the method used. For simplicity, the axoneme is drawn on an assumption that it splits into two groups of outer doublets when shear force is applied with the glass needle.

Figure 6: Figure 1 of [14]

or unfold when sheared, in a reversible manner. Although mechanical properties of nexin links had just started to be unveiled, it has shown the importance of shear resistance in axonemal mechanics.

Lindemann & al [12] first discover a consequence of this shear resistance: the counterbend phenomenon. When bending rat sperm cell demembranated flagella rendered passive with vanadate, not only the first bend but also **a second bend is generated on the distal part of the flagellum, opposing to the first one**. A reversible behavior is observed: the counterbend disappears when letting go external forcing. Digestion with trypsin or elastase (a substance supposed to have an effect principally on nexin links) prevents the counterbend to form. This suggests that **the counterbend is due to protein linkage in the flagellum, probably only nexin**. This phenomenon seems to be **due to the minimization of shear between doublets. Since one imposes a bend, a shear is imposed: to compensate this shear, a counterbend should exist**. If this is the case, one should expect no shear at the flagellum tip. To probe this, measurement of the shear angle – the difference of tangent angles between a point on the flagellum and the basal body attachment – is performed. Indeed, as seen in Figure 7 the shear angle diminishes from the microprobe towards the tip where the shear angle goes to zero but it is even sometimes negative. It is important to remember that rat sperm flagella are much thicker than other mammalian sperm flagella: they have outer dense fibers (ODF) on most of their length – but disappears near the tip – surrounding the axoneme and attached to outer doublets. This changes the effective shear displacement which is proportional to the interdistance in the bending plane: ODF amplify effective shear

Figure 7: Shear angles in the counterbend for a rat sperm cell bent to 3.1 radians, with inset of the experiment that also shows the circle used for curvature measurement, thus the shear angle. Bar is $20\mu m$. Figure adapted from [12]

force and could explain the excedent shear angle near the tip. Assuming that elastic resistance to sliding is due to nexin links, using direct experimental data and previous values of flexural rigidity, they give an estimate of nexin resistance as a function of relative displacement. **These elastic links don't seem to be hookean but shear-thinning**, for values of $k_{nexin} = 1.6 - 9.7 * 10^{-5} N/m$. This value is at least 10 times smaller than in Minoura & al [14] In any case, the counterbend phenomenon gives us a tool to measure a combination of shear elasticity and flexural rigidity resistance to bending.

Pelle & al [18] exploited this idea on sea urchin sperm. Unlike rat sperm flagella, sea urchin sperm flagella do not exhibit ODFs. Following the protocol of Lindemann & al [12] they were anyway able to **see a counterbend**, also reversible. Measuring shear angle shows that shear induced by the counterbend seems again to compensate shear induced by the bend. However, for higher shear – when bending increases – this is not true anymore: a positive shear angle is still present between the base and the tip. This can be due to **mechanical compression of the axoneme** which would reduce doublet interdistance thus the effective shear, or due to detachment of elastic linkages. Cutting the basal part of the flagellum reduces significantly the counterbend and bending near the tip on an intact axoneme does not create a counterbend on the proximal part of the flagellum. These observations comfort the fact that microtubule sliding causes this phenomenon: **no-sliding is a necessary condition for interdoublet shear**. A model of linear elasticity allows experimental data fitting better than a non-linear model. The ratio of shear resistance to flexural rigidity is found to be $E_S/EI = 0.03 - 0.08\mu m^{-2}$. In order to separate these two parameters, one needs another experiment. Using data from Okuno [16] one finds a (true) flexural rigidity $EI = 10^{-22} N.m^2/rad$ and a shear resistance $E_S = 6pN/rad$. The latter is 10 times lower than what Minoura & al [14] found. Maybe **shear resistance of flagella could be different in Chlamydomonas than in sea urchin sperm or even rat sperm**, which would explain the difference in

result.

Xu & al [28] complete part of the puzzle by examining the **counterbend phenomenon on Chlamydomonas**. Flexural rigidity and shear resistance are both determined for wild type and different mutants: pf3-cnk11-6 does not have nexin-dynein regulatory complex (N-DRC) while pf13A does not have outer dynein arms neither inner dynein arm c. Two experiments are made. The first one, as in Pelle & al [18], quantifies the effect of shear resistance compared to bending resistance, $\beta^2 \equiv k_S/EI$ where k_S is the shear stiffness. A cell is held with a micropipette, a microneedle locally induces bending but a counterbend is also observed. By modelling an elastic beam with resistance to sliding and fitting to the experimental data, one finds that $\beta_{wt}^2 = 0.111 \pm 0.054 \mu m^{-2}$ which is similar to the value of Pelle & al. $\beta_{pf3-cnk11-6}^2$ and β_{pf13A}^2 are lower than for the wild type.

Figure 8: Measurement of the apparent flexural rigidity of the flagellar axoneme with optical tweezers. Video micrographs (a–c) and corresponding models (a’–c’) show the flagellum approaching, pushing, and pulling on a trapped bead. The trapped bead functions as a mechanical spring and allows to measure the resistance of the tip to deflection, the inverse of the tip compliance, ultimately linked to flexural rigidity. Figure taken from [28]

Flagellar tip compliance is then measured by trapping a bead within an optical trap, sticking it to the tip of a flagellum with the help of a pipette and pulling, as seen in Figure 8. The tip compliance quantifies how much is the tip moving with a certain applied force. Data is fitted to a counterbend model developed by Gadelha & al [7] accounting for both flexural rigidity and shear resistance, knowing β^2 from the first experiment. **Apparent flexural rigidity increases with length.** One finds a (true) flexural rigidity $EI = 8.4 \pm 2.8 * 10^{-22} N.m^2$ for the wild type. This value is still **compatible with a model of connected microtubules accounting for bending stiffness**. However it is 10 times higher than in Pelle & al [18] – determined from Okuno’s experiments [16] – even though the resistance ratio is similar: disagreement is on the apparent flexural rigidity measured, potentially coming from differences between radial spokes in Chlamydomonas and sea urchin sperm. Mutant values of flexural rigidity are not statistically significantly different. Shear resistance of wild type

is $k_S = 79.6 \pm 10.5 \text{ pN/rad}$, which agrees with Minoura & al [14]. Shear resistance is twice as small in mutants. **Even with vanadate – relaxed, detached state – dynein arms contribute to shear resistance.** Values of structural element can be untangle thanks to these specific experiments: $k_S[\text{NDRC}] \approx 35 \text{ pN/rad}$ and $k_S[\text{outer dynein} + \text{inner dynein c}] \approx 37 \text{ pN/rad}$.

We saw two main mechanical quantities of the axoneme of motile cilia: bending stiffness and shear resistance. These quantities are useful but not complete: knowledge of viscous properties of the axoneme are still parcellar and indirect. Mondal & al [15] showed that surrounding fluid viscosity does not play a role in initiation of beating, consequently concluding that internal dissipation is essential to beating. On the other hand, most experiments probe static and mostly linear responses of the axoneme. However, the complexity of this material makes it likely to have a non-linear, dynamic behaviour.

3 Mechanical properties of primary cilia

Introduction I continue this review with primary flagella, as they have been discarded as useless organelles for many years until their role in mechanosensing started to be understood and attention raised to the importance of their mechanical properties. Primary flagella are almost ubiquitous in the human body and present in most animal cells. In humans, they can be encountered in kidney and other organs as protrusions of epithelial cells. In kidneys they extend from the dorsal surface of the cell to the lumen of the nephron, a flow channel supposed to filtrate the substance flowing within it. As seen in Figure 9, primary cilia are well anchored to the cell thanks to a complex intracellular anchoring. Their basal body is the mother centriole which is connected to the daughter centriole and the nucleus by striated rootlets. The basal body is firmly implanted in the cell thanks to these and a network of microtubules in the actin cortex.

Figure 9: Idealized view of the structure of a primary cilia under flow. Bending – here due to external flow – provokes an intracellular calcium increase. Figure taken from [2]

A landmark paper is the one of Schwartz & al [25] in which they analyze mechanical properties of primary flagella of rat kangaroo kidney epithelial cells to see if these mechanical properties can be appropriate for mechanosensing. Primary cilia of Rat Kangaroo Epithelial Cells are fixed on a substrate, a flow is applied perpendicular to the resting cilium axis. Using two models of elastic beams in the Stokes regime, with resistive force theory, one tries to infer flexural rigidity of the axoneme and to assess the predictive validity of each model. Heavy elastica model seems to give consistent predictions to experiments within a certain flow range. Assumptions of this model are that the cilium is rigidly attached to its base (zero displacement, zero slope) and that bending occurs passively, from external forces. It thus implies that **the primary cilium is well attached to the cell**, potentially to the cytoskeleton even though **there seems to be some level of rotation at the base on micrographs**, and that **there is no active mechanism to bending** as expected. Both models give a similar order of flexural rigidity of $EI = 10^{-23} N.m^2$, which is 10 to 100 times smaller than for motile (9+2)-cilia, depending of the bending direction. This is consistent with the fact that for motile cilia bending stiffness is mostly due to connections between microtubule doublets. However, a constant fluid drag with distance from cell surface was assumed – due to a constant velocity profile – and could be a source of systematic error in flexural rigidity. Interestingly, tip fluctuations within a micron are observed and interpreted as thermal motion – which can be verified to be a consistent explanation for now.

Several papers improved on the work of Schwartz & al [25] and tried to give a mechanical understanding of the fact that intracellular calcium concentration increased with flagellum bending, a candidate mechanism for mechanosensing through chemical signaling [19]. Without entering in details, Liu & al [13] used a similar model as previously but accounted for rotation at base using a linear velocity profile. Rydholm & al [23] incorporated a viscoelastic model of the apical membrane relating bending to membrane stress. Young & al [29] also model the apical membrane to explain how rotation at the base under shear flow increases membrane tension at the base and how it could lead to the opening of ion channels. Based on experiments from Ishijima & al [9] on motile cilia, membrane mechanical properties don't seem to play a major role in the bending mechanism – unlike in mechanosensing – so we will not talk in detail about it.

Downs & al [5] build on Schwartz's work [25] without trying to explain the calcium increase, but rather focuses on mere mechanical responses to fluid flow: equilibrium shapes with and without flow, relaxation patterns, all combined with enhanced imaging. IMCD cells are grown on a substrate with proteins that target flagellum for imaging. One imposes a laminar constant flow with a syringe pump. Shapes before and during flow are recorded: initial shape is injected in the model while stationary underflow shape is what the model should aim to reproduce by tuning flexural rigidity. One observes smooth bending for some flagella as expected, but also either **kinks in the axoneme** (see Figure ??) or a **finite base angle** (10° on average), let alone **curved initial shapes**. Kinks in the axoneme show that part of the cilium does not experience flow. It can be because that part is within the membrane, or under glycocalyx. Com-

Figure 10: A kinked axoneme micrograph. Figure taken from [5]

bined with rotation at base, this shows a potential cell regulation of underflow length, thus tuning mechanosensing. Another possibility to explain kinks would be that EI is greater near the base. One also observes **non-elasticity** from relaxation patterns: **cilia don't always return to their original shape. They sometimes also passed their initial shape**, suggesting **active bending** can occur. Flexural rigidity is calculated to be of $EI = 2.1 \pm 0.45 * 10^{-22} N.m^2$. This is 17 times the value of Schwartz & al [25]. This might be explained from the fact that a 100 higher shear stress is applied, that rotation at base was not accounted for, nor was the varying drag profile or from the use of different cell lines. Observed plastic or active bending behaviors may also explain the difference with previous measurements.

Considering that 9 independent microtubules would give a value of $EI = 7 * 10^{-23} N.m^2$, it is plausible that **microtubule doublets are not independent but rather cross-linked. However**, this conclusion goes against previous measurements of flexural rigidity that rather conclude for an absence of linking between doublets. How can we reconcile our knowledge of the axonemal structure? In any case, the new observed behaviours and values for flexural rigidity put into question several assumptions in the model. In particular, the fact that the flagellum is an isotropic, homogeneous material can be a strong issue. Indeed, **microtubules have been found to not be isotropic** which may partly explain the variability in their flexural rigidity measurements [11] – namely with length or measurement methods, probing static or dynamic mechanical response to external forcing.

Looking at relaxation patterns of the cilium in a viscous medium can also give direct information on flexural rigidity. Battle & al [2] look at relaxation patterns of previously bent cilia of MDCK cells with an optical trap. This allows determination of flexural rigidity $EI = 3.6 \pm 0.8 * 10^{-23} N.m^2$. This value is compared to those obtained from experiments in which cilia tips are attached to a bead that is deflected with an optical trap – in the spirit of [28], see Figure 8 –, while measuring the required force to deflect the whole. The flexural rigidity found is of $EI = 2.5 \pm 1.5 * 10^{-23} N.m^2$, in agreement with the former experiment as well as previous experiments on primary cilia, except Downs & al [5]. This result is consistent with weak microtubule coupling, putting the dilemma on axoneme internal structure on the scene again. However, it seems that the relaxation pattern can be best modelled by a double exponential, indicating **another source of resistance to bending, which can only be internal**. A rotational spring at the base could be the cause of this other relaxation timescale, thus leading

Fig. 1 Schematic and inset image of optically trapped primary cilium. Location of optical trap indicated by circle. The cilium projects above the cell body and so appears as a dot in the microscopic image

Figure 11: Schematics of an optically trapped cilium tip. Figure 1 from [6]

to an underestimate of measured flexural rigidity. To unveil properties of this rotational spring, angular fluctuations are observed without external forcing. It seems that **there is a limited hinge at the base** as the rod stays rigid but has a fluctuating finite base angle, whereas the deflection angle is constant throughout the flagellum. Hinging is also confirmed by a L^2 dependency of the mean square displacement. The rotation seems to be three-dimensional and no anisotropy is found in this movement. In particular, eccentricity measurements show that **there does not seem to be a preferred bending plane**, on the contrary to motile cilia where the bending plane depends on the basal foot position. To know the origin of this hinge, analysis of fluctuations of cilia tips are made with control cells, and cells that are ATP-depleted or myosin-inhibited. In both cases cilia mean-square displacements show a significant drop in amplitude compared to control cells: this is indicative of an active motion, that seems to be due to **ATP-driven myosin in the actin cortex exerting forces on the basal body**. Lastly, simultaneous fluctuations of centrioles and cilium are observed thanks to marking proteins. A positive xy-correlation is observed, indicating that the effective hinge point is below the basal body. All this confirms that **there is a limited hinge whose effective pivot point is below the basal body, and whose origin is acto-myosin-induced active fluctuations of the basal body**. But how do active basal body fluctuations and a limited basal hinge change the bending stiffness of primary cilia?

Trying to answer that question, Resnick [22] tries to quantify the mechanical properties of the basal body. An optical trap is concentrated close to the cilium tip location (similar to Figure 11, supposed to trigger a point force response of the flagellum). The tip position is recorded indirectly from diffraction

patterns of the laser diffracting through the tip. The force exerted to the cilium tip is deduced by the gradient of intensity in the trap between the tip and the waist, function of the tip spatial position with respect to the waist. Using an optical trap on mCCD cell cilia tip reveals an oscillatory response, which can be understood when modelling an elastic beam under viscous drag with a non-linear rotational spring at the base. *Caution* should be taken, though, because it is not clear for us as to how a resonant response can exist if the excitation is static (the beam): what is the source of energy? Why isn't the cilium tip simply stopping at the equilibrium position (e.g., at the optical trap axis)? Caution aside, spring constants (linear and quadratic) are obtained when the model matches experimental measurements, in particular oscillation frequency and amplitude are retrieved. Primary cilia of mCCD cells thus seem to behave as elastic beams with a non-linear rotary spring at the base, which in viscous media with periodic forcing can be seen as a Duffing oscillator (of frequency $f_0 \sim 57Hz$ here). One finds for the rotary spring $k_{linear} = 4.6 * 10^{-12} N/rad$ and $k_{quadratic} = -1 * 10^{-10} N/rad^2$. The non-linear part is thus softening the flagellum, and is what defines the upper boundary in flagellar length. A Duffing oscillator that could trigger regulation of flagellar length and opening of the diffusion barrier between cilioplasm and cytoplasm. However, cilium length is here of around $2\mu m$, and mCCD cells have a mechanism of cilium length autoregulation, which is apparently not the case for MDCK cells. Moreover an average value of $EI = 1.5 * 10^{-23} N.m^2$ is taken for data fitting. It is thus unclear if such a Duffing regulator would exist in other cells types and if spring constants calculated here would be the same for longer cilia.

Flaherty & al [6] tries to tackle – at last – the length-dependence issue of flexural rigidity, or equivalently persistence length $l_p \equiv EI/k_B T$. Mean square displacement (MSD) of an optically trapped cilium tip is measured (see Figure 11): it grows with cilium length, showing that **longer cilia are stiffer than shorter ones. A model of an isotropic, clamped elastic beam is inconsistent with the data**: the derived MSD grows with cilium length instead of decreasing. Basal body fluctuations, however, lead to a decreasing MSD with cilium length, which is qualitatively consistent with experiments. According to our knowledge of microtubules [11], cilia cannot be purely isotropic but should rather be considered as transversely isotropic. A model accounting for this kind of anisotropy fits well experimental data but only when basal body fluctuations are accounted for. In particular, transverse anisotropy is what makes the persistence length length-dependent. Assuming independence of microtubule doublets within the axoneme:

$$l_p = 18 \frac{l_p^\infty}{1 + \frac{\pi^2 E_z}{\alpha^2 G} + \frac{\pi^4 E_z}{\alpha^4 E_\theta}}$$

where $\alpha = L/R$, $l_p^\infty = \pi h R^3 \frac{E_z}{k_B T}$. $h = 2.7nm$ is the wall thickness of a microtubule and $R = 12.5nm$ is the middle radius of a microtubule. E_z, E_θ, G are respectively the axial Young's modulus, the azimuthal Young's modulus and the shear modulus of single microtubules. Interestingly, the persistence length of a single microtubule is length-dependent as it depends on the aspect ratio α , which by absence of crosslinking is also the case for cilium persistence-length. It is found that the azimuthal modulus is not relevant for data fitting. On the contrary basal body fluctuations are necessary. In conclusion, **cilia stiffen**

with length. Actin-myosin-driven basal body fluctuations transmitted to the cilium are necessary to explain this phenomena. **Microtubule doublets are modelled as transversely isotropic shells** and lead to good experimental agreement. Different values are found $E_z = 1.4GPa$, $G = 2kPa$ (in the low-strain regime) and $\theta_{BB} = 0.01\mu m^3/pN$ which is the basal body MSD divided by the internal basal-body-to-cilium stiffness, i.e. how much MSD is transmitted from the basal body to the cilium tip. Microtubule mechanical properties – E_z and G – are consistent with previous experiments [11]. Using this persistence length formula, one finds agreement with values from Battle & al [2], but not with Schwarz & al [25] nor with Downs & al [5]. Indeed, none of those two papers take into account basal body fluctuations. This does not, however, explain why cilia measured by Downs & al are apparently stiffer than longer cilia measured by Schwarz & al, which might be explained from plastic behavior together with high flow rate experiments.

So primary cilia are actually not passive but exhibit ATP-driven basal body fluctuations transmitted to the axoneme via a limited hinge at the base, that change their apparent flexural rigidity: cilia stiffen with length and are not isotropic since microtubules are not. No longitudinal shear experiment – in contrast with motile flagella – has been done as far as we know, and variations in flexural rigidity measurements are not fully explained yet, but could be a hint of inelastic or dynamic mechanical behaviour.

4 Summary of the results and discussion

Knowledge of mechanical properties of the axoneme of eukaryotic flagella has evolved in the last decades. Crucially, all modelling attempts started with the Euler-Bernoulli elastic beam theory. For this model only one parameter really matters: flexural rigidity. Assuming that deactivating or removing components of the axoneme only change the flexural rigidity – but not the ideal elastic beam behaviour – also allowed to determine componental contributions to bending resistance. In motile cilia as in primary cilia, this model fails: resistance to bending increases with length.

For motile cilia it is because of shear resistance – i.e. resistance to inter-doublet sliding – probably due to an elastic binding, part of the nexin-dynein regulatory complex, between microtubule doublets. In fact this resistance to microtubule sliding causes a mechanism that could not exist otherwise: the counterbend, present in mammalian flagella as well as *Chlamydomonas*. When incorporating shear resistance to the former model, two different experiments are now needed to measure flexural rigidity and shear resistance. There seem to be a common experimental value for the ratio of shear resistance to flexural rigidity of about $\beta^2 \approx 0.1 \pm 0.05\mu m^{-2}$, but apparent flexural rigidity, i.e., torque divided by change in curvature when bending occurs – is not completely consensual. It is possible that resistance to sliding is an order of magnitude higher in *Chlamydomonas* than in mammalian sperm flagella, which would explain lower values of intrinsic – true – flexural rigidity. Despite these disagreements, details of mechanical properties of the internal structure are found. There exist a rigor state corresponding to crosslinking dynein arms and a relaxed state corresponding to weakly binding dynein arms, because the apparent flexural rigidity is

higher in the rigor wave which appears in the absence of ATP. Indeed even if shear resistance accounts for part of this apparent bending resistance, dynein arms have also been shown to contribute greatly to shear resistance. Apparent resistance to bending is lower parallel to the bending plane and similar to when ATP and vanadate are present in the solution, which indicates that most dynein arms are disengaged. Also, and luckily, even the lowest determined value of true flexural rigidity is compatible with the fact that it is microtubule doublets, connected together, that are resisting to bending.

For primary cilia, there might not be shear resistance because of the simpler axonemal structure, but flexural rigidity measurements are affected by a number of factors. First, there is a limited hinge boundary condition – as opposed to clamped – at the basal end, with the effective pivot point localized below the basal body. There are ATP-driven active oscillations of the basal body, transmitted to the axoneme, probably coming from the actin-myosin cortex. Finally, since microtubules are not isotropic the axoneme cannot be either. Hence its persistence length, or equally its flexural rigidity, is length-dependent. This last argument is also valid for motile flagella, actually. However, the value of Downs & al is still unexplained by these factors, which is intriguing, at least as much as the inelastic behaviors they observe such as the kink.

As [11] explained for microtubules, perhaps the type of measurement matters a lot as it probes different responses of the material. Indeed different methods used can be static (hydrodynamic static response) or dynamic (thermal fluctuations), by a localized force (optical trap), a non-localized force (hydrodynamic drag) or even no force at all (thermal fluctuations). The amplitude of the forces exerted could also be a factor. Actually, probing passive material response in a wider range of amplitude and frequency would show how far is the axoneme from being a mere elastic rod.

References

- [1] Shoji A. Baba. “Flexural Rigidity and Elastic Constant of Cilia”. In: *Journal of Experimental Biology* 56.2 (Apr. 1972), pp. 459–467. ISSN: 0022-0949. DOI: 10.1242/jeb.56.2.459. eprint: <https://journals.biologists.com/jeb/article-pdf/56/2/459/1341432/459.pdf>. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1242/jeb.56.2.459>.
- [2] Christopher Battle et al. “Intracellular and extracellular forces drive primary cilia movement”. In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 112.5 (2015), pp. 1410–1415. ISSN: 0027-8424. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1421845112. eprint: <https://www.pnas.org/content/112/5/1410.full.pdf>. URL: <https://www.pnas.org/content/112/5/1410>.
- [3] Beeby M, Ferreira JL, Tripp P, Albers SV, Mitchell DR. “Propulsive nanomachines: the convergent evolution of archaella, flagella and cilia”. In: *FEMS Microbiol. Rev.* 44.3 (2020), pp. 253–304. DOI: 10.1093/femsre/fuaa006.
- [4] Brumley DR, Wan KY, Polin M, Goldstein RE. “Flagellar synchronization through direct hydrodynamic interactions”. In: *Elife* (2014), e2750. DOI: 10.7554/eLife.02750.

- [5] Downs ME, Nguyen AM, Herzog FA, Hoey DA, Jacobs CR. “An experimental and computational analysis of primary cilia deflection under fluid flow [published correction appears in *Comput. Methods Biomech. Biomed. Engin.* 2014;17(4):459]”. In: *Comput. Methods Biomech. Biomed. Engin.* 17.1 (2014), pp. 2–10. DOI: 10.1080/10255842.2011.653784.
- [6] Flaherty, J., Feng, Z., Peng, Z. et al. “Primary cilia have a length-dependent persistence length”. In: *Biomech. Model Mechanobiol.* 19 (2020), pp. 445–460. DOI: 10.1007/s10237-019-01220-7.
- [7] Hermes Gadêlha, Eamonn A. Gaffney, and Alain Goriely. “The counterbend phenomenon in flagellar axonemes and cross-linked filament bundles”. In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 110.30 (2013), pp. 12180–12185. ISSN: 0027-8424. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1302113110. eprint: <https://www.pnas.org/content/110/30/12180.full.pdf>. URL: <https://www.pnas.org/content/110/30/12180>.
- [8] Gibbons BH, Gibbons IR. “Properties of flagellar ”rigor waves” formed by abrupt removal of adenosine triphosphate from actively swimming sea urchin sperm”. In: *J Cell Biol.* 63.3 (1974), pp. 970–985. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.63.3.970.
- [9] Ishijima S, Hiramoto Y. “Flexural rigidity of echinoderm sperm flagella”. In: *Cell Struct Funct.* 19.6 (1994), pp. 349–362. DOI: 10.1247/csf.19.349.
- [10] Ishikawa T. “Axoneme Structure from Motile Cilia”. In: *Cold Spring Harb Perspect Biol* 9.1 (2017), a028076. DOI: 10.1101/cshperspect.a028076.
- [11] Mahito Kikumoto et al. “Flexural Rigidity of Individual Microtubules Measured by a Buckling Force with Optical Traps”. In: *Biophysical Journal* 90.5 (2006), pp. 1687–1696. ISSN: 0006-3495. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1529/biophysj.104.055483>. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0006349506723578>.
- [12] Lindemann CB, Macauley LJ, Lesich KA. “The counterbend phenomenon in dynein-disabled rat sperm flagella and what it reveals about the interdouplet elasticity”. In: *Biophys. J.* 89.2 (2005), pp. 1165–1174. DOI: 10.1529/biophysj.105.060681.
- [13] Liu W, Murcia NS, Duan Y, et al. “Mechanoregulation of intracellular Ca²⁺ concentration is attenuated in collecting duct of monocilium-impaired orpk mice”. In: *Am. J. Physiol. Renal Physiol.* 289.5 (2005), F978–F988. DOI: 10.1152/ajprenal.00260.2004.
- [14] Minoura I, Yagi T, Kamiya R. “Direct measurement of inter-douplet elasticity in flagellar axonemes”. In: *Cell Struct Funct.* 24.1 (1999), pp. 27–33. DOI: 10.1247/csf.24.27.
- [15] Debasmita Mondal, Ronojoy Adhikari, and Purna Sharma. “Internal friction controls active ciliary oscillations near the instability threshold”. In: *Science Advances* 6.33 (2020), eabb0503. DOI: 10.1126/sciadv.abb0503. eprint: <https://www.science.org/doi/pdf/10.1126/sciadv.abb0503>. URL: <https://www.science.org/doi/abs/10.1126/sciadv.abb0503>.
- [16] Okuno M. “Inhibition and relaxation of sea urchin sperm flagella by vanadate”. In: *J Cell Biol.* 85.3 (1980), pp. 712–725. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.85.3.712.

- [17] Satir P. “Studies on cilia. 3. Further studies on the cilium tip and a ”sliding filament” model of ciliary motility”. In: *J Cell Biol.* 39 (1968), pp. 77–94. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.39.1.77.
- [18] Pelle DW, Brokaw CJ, Lesich KA, Lindemann CB. “Mechanical properties of the passive sea urchin sperm flagellum”. In: *Cell Motil. Cytoskeleton* 66.9 (2009), pp. 721–735. DOI: 10.1002/cm.20401.
- [19] Praetorius HA, Spring KR. “Bending the MDCK cell primary cilium increases intracellular calcium”. In: *J. Membr. Biol.* 184.1 (2001), pp. 71–79. DOI: 10.1007/s00232-001-0075-4.
- [20] E. M. Purcell. “Life at low Reynolds number”. In: *American Journal of Physics* 45.1 (1977), pp. 3–11. DOI: 10.1119/1.10903. eprint: <https://doi.org/10.1119/1.10903>. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1119/1.10903>.
- [21] Greta Quaranta. “On the dynamics of *C. reinhardtii* subject to external periodic flows: A model system for synchronization in biology”. English. PhD thesis. Delft University of Technology, 2018. ISBN: 978-94-6186-943-2. DOI: 10.4233/uuid:6afc536c-79cf-4406-8b20-33a757ddffba.
- [22] Resnick A. “Mechanical properties of a primary cilium as measured by resonant oscillation”. In: *Biophys. J.* 109.1 (2015), pp. 18–25. DOI: 10.1016/j.bpj.2015.05.031.
- [23] Rydholm S, Zwart G, Kowalewski JM, Kamali-Zare P, Frisk T, Brismar H. “Mechanical properties of primary cilia regulate the response to fluid flow.” In: *Am. J. Physiol. Renal Physiol.* 298.5 (2010), F1096–F1102. DOI: 10.1152/ajprenal.00657.2009.
- [24] Peter Satir et al. “The mechanochemical cycle of the dynein arm”. In: *Cell Motility* 1.3 (1981), pp. 303–327. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/cm.970010304>. eprint: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1002/cm.970010304>. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/cm.970010304>.
- [25] E. A. Schwartz et al. “Analysis and modeling of the primary cilium bending response to fluid shear”. In: *American Journal of Physiology-Renal Physiology* 272.1 (1997). PMID: 9039059, F132–F138. DOI: 10.1152/ajprenal.1997.272.1.F132. eprint: <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajprenal.1997.272.1.F132>. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajprenal.1997.272.1.F132>.
- [26] Summers KE, Gibbons IR. “Adenosine triphosphate-induced sliding of tubules in trypsin-treated flagella of sea-urchin sperm”. In: *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 68.12 (1971), pp. 3082–3096. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.68.12.3092.
- [27] FD Warner and NC Zanetti. “Properties of microtubule sliding disintegration in isolated tetrahymena cilia”. In: *Journal of Cell Biology* 86.2 (Aug. 1980), pp. 436–445. ISSN: 0021-9525. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.86.2.436. eprint: <https://rupress.org/jcb/article-pdf/86/2/436/1074291/436.pdf>. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1083/jcb.86.2.436>.
- [28] Xu G, Wilson KS, Okamoto RJ, Shao JY, Dutcher SK, Bayly PV. “Flexural Rigidity and Shear Stiffness of Flagella Estimated from Induced Bends and Counterbends”. In: *Biophys J.* 110.12 (2016), pp. 2759–2768. DOI: 10.1016/j.bpj.2016.05.017.

- [29] Young YN, Downs M, Jacobs CR. “Dynamics of the primary cilium in shear flow”. In: *Biophys. J.* 103.4 (2012), pp. 629–639. DOI: 10.1016/j.bpj.2012.07.009.